

“Impact of Role Conflict among Female Teachers at Home and Workplace: A Sociological Analysis”

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Abstract:

Role conflict is a concept that comes from teachers' overburdening of expectations when they are required to meet several obligations for other parties in addition to teaching. Teachers may be stressed as a result of their overworked lives, insufficient pay or bad physical conditions at school, ethnic conflict in the community, or physical violence in the school or classroom.

Aims: To study the socio-economic profile of the female teachers and the effect of role conflict on female teacher's job performance in primary school.

Methods: 300 participants were surveyed using planned interviews and observation as part of the current study's information collection process. Through purposeful sampling, the respondents were selected.

Results: The results showed that The majority of the people who answered the survey, 58.33%, were in the middle age group of 36 and above; half of the respondents are Hindu; approximately 2/3rd (68.33%) belong to the OBC SC ST category, which shows the lower status in society; a large number (41.67%) are unmarried; and the majority (58.33%) of the respondents are unmarried, in which those who are married have two or more children within the 1 lakh to 2 lakh annual income group. Role conflict and socioeconomic position do not significantly correlate. Conflict tendencies are more psychological and attitudinal, therefore one's natural ability to be accommodating and how they view the circumstance have a big impact. The role conflict could be impacted by the female teachers' caste. Female teachers from upper castes may encounter less role conflict because their families are generally in better shape than those from lower castes. Female primary school teachers in the SC category experience more role conflict than their counterparts in the ST, OBC, and GEN categories.

Keywords: Education, Teacher, Role Conflict, Job Satisfaction.

Introduction:-

Education is humanity's one-of-a-kind invention. Without education, man continues to live as an animal. Education is a force that transforms a man into a man. Every man possesses some inner potentialities, and teachers play a crucial role in bringing these potentialities to fruition. The backbone of the entire educational system, as well as the nation, is the teacher. In our educational system, the teacher is the nucleus of the whole. In light of shifting needs in the classroom, the teacher's job will have to evolve. “A school without a teacher is like a body without a soul, a skeleton without flesh, or a shadow entity without blood.” The teacher is the benchmark by which the nation's achievement and aspirations are measured. The value and potential of a country are assessed. In the teaching process, the teacher plays a crucial role. The way he teaches and interacts with his students has an impact on their future personalities. The teacher is one of the most important aspects of the institution's learning environment. The entirety of human knowledge expands at once, at an ever-increasing rate, offering the best to the next generation. Teachers prescribe and convey this type of knowledge from generation to generation through the formal educational system.

Schools are small versions of society that represent it. As a result, schools should be well-organized, with enough teaching and learning facilities and a happy teaching staff. In addition, the

Right to Education emphasizes that schools should provide basic infrastructure, qualified teaching staff, and a better learning environment. When the Education Commission (1964-66) observed after independence, it paid special attention to the teachers. "The quality competence and character of teachers are without a doubt the most important variables that determine the quality of education and its contribution to national development. Nothing is more vital than ensuring a steady supply of high-quality recruits for the teaching profession, as well as providing them with the finest possible professional preparation and working conditions in which they can be completely effective." Based on the preceding explanation, we may deduce that the teacher serves as a torchbearer for students. This is why they are known as nation-builders. For the aim of achieving educational objectives, teachers are supposed to act as an organizer, a transmitter of necessary knowledge and ability, demonstrations, a planner, and an Education is humanity's one-of-a-kind invention. Without education, man continues to live as an animal. Education is a force that transforms a man into a man. Every man possesses some inner potentialities, and teachers play a crucial role in bringing these potentialities to fruition. The backbone of the entire educational system, as well as the nation, is the teacher. In our educational system, the teacher is the nucleus of the whole. In light of shifting needs in the classroom, the teacher's job will have to evolve.

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Teachers' collaboration with other schools and learning system components results in a better learning environment. When a teacher is confronted with incompatible and contradictory demands from several key reference groups in the school as well as from other areas of society, it makes it difficult for him to fulfill his position satisfactorily. Role conflict occurs when a person is asked to simultaneously play out various roles with contradicting expectations, according to this hypothesis. Each social function entails a set of rights, responsibilities, expectations, norms, and behaviors that a person must confront and uphold. The model is based on the observation that people behave in predictable ways and that an individual's behavior is context-specific, depending on social status and other circumstances. When he senses competing

expectations, a scenario known as role conflict arises. The word "role conflict" is a versatile one that can signify a lot of different things to different people. Such contradicting situations cause a struggle in the teacher's head, which manifests itself either as aggressive behavior or withdrawal from reality. They may also break from group standards and teacher behavior norms. Only a teacher understands the fundamental requirements of a learning system, but teachers are rarely involved in decision-making. Negative self-worth, a lack of opportunities to demonstrate one's abilities, and a lack of sufficient credit for creative and innovative efforts can all contribute to a reduction in an individual's ability, working style, and function. Teachers' professional dedication, teacher demeanor, and frustration tolerance may all be influenced by role conflict. It is thought that looking into these characteristics will help explain the issue of role conflict among secondary school teachers. These concerns and assumptions have led to the current study.

Role of Teacher:-

She is a daughter, sister, friend, wife, mother, teacher, and the list goes on and on in terms of a woman's function in her life. She also has a significant impact on the growth of a family, society, and nation as a whole. Teaching is thought to be an appealing vocation for a woman who wishes to work in the social field. In Indian society, teaching is a very comfortable job for women. Women enter the teaching profession for a variety of reasons. These include short work days at school, no work during school holidays, and so on. These are some of the key reasons why women choose to teach. Primary school teaching is the most important and necessary job in the educational system. School teachers pass on knowledge and cultural values to youngsters, as well as preparing them for further education and their future lives. However, due to societal pressures on teachers, female teachers have numerous problems in fulfilling their roles in the home and at school. They must devote time and energy to both their family and classroom responsibilities. As a result of the challenges of incompatible performing roles, role conflict arises. As a result, the current study explores whether female primary school teachers experience role conflict, if so, to what extent, and what factors contribute to the role conflict.

Teacher Definitions:-

Education is critical to the development of any country or state. As a result, it is necessary to prioritize the educational system, which is only achievable with skilled professors. The educational system revolves around the teacher

Gandhiji says, “Only the living touch of the teacher could provide education of the heart.” “Teacher is the image of Brahma,” says Manu, an ancient Indian

guru. "Gurur Brahma, Gurur Vishnu, Guru Devo Maheshwaraha, Guru Sakshath para Brahma, Thatshmai Sri Guruve Namaha," says a Hindu Indian prayer, "The teacher is the Brahma, the creator, Lord Vishnu, and also the Lord Maheshwara."

"The teacher is the genuine maker of history," according to H.G. Wells.

Concept And Meaning of Role Conflict:-

Role conflict is a concept that comes from teachers' overburdening of expectations when they are required to meet several obligations for other parties in addition to teaching. Of course, not all teachers' expectations are shared, and several studies have documented non-consensual teacher expectations. The majority of this research has focused on norms, and the majority of writers have interpreted their findings as signs of role conflict. In the research on teacher behavior, several types of role conflict have been proposed. Evidence that people's social statuses contain different forms of teacher conduct is a common finding understood as role conflict. Teachers, school principals, parents, pupils, teacher trainers, teacher trainers, people from different social groups, people from rural and urban communities, and so on have all been observed to have discrepancies in the United Kingdom and the United States (Kelsall and Kelsall 1969, Biddle 1979). The majority of this research has claimed that these differences will generate problems for teachers since persons who embrace different norms will likely exert competing pressures on teachers to conform. However, most studies do not show that other people will genuinely create such pressures, that teachers are aware of these differing norms, or that teachers are bothered by their looks. Many authors interpret this awareness as role conflict since some teachers recognize that others have different standards for their behavior. Studies on such awareness have been published in several nations, and a significant investigation has been published that reports similar findings from Australia, the United Kingdom, New Zealand, and the United States, based on national samples of teachers (Adams 1970). In all four nations studied, normative discrepancies were discovered. Some findings were consistent across nations; for example, teachers were likely to see themselves as at conflict with administrators and other school officials over topics like willing acceptance of non-professional obligations and with parents over curricular matters. Other findings were country-specific; for example, presumptive conflict between teachers and school authorities was highest in Australia, while parent-teacher conflict was highest in the United Kingdom. Teachers' impressions of normative gaps among various groups of people may not necessarily imply that these judgments are accurate. Biddle et al. (1966) offered evidence that teachers systematically

mislead administrators', parents, and other school-related elements' genuine views. Perceived normative discrepancies, on the other hand, have been linked to indications of stress in both teachers and members of other occupations (Biddle 1979).

Role conflict between norms linked with teaching and coaching, teaching and counseling, and teaching and administrative tasks has been reported in studies. The majority of the research, however, has focused on the competing demands of teaching and homemaking. The majority of studies on this latter topic have been published in the United States, where women make up the majority of teachers and where interest in female role conflicts has recently exploded. Conflicts of this nature are also known to cause tension. Finally, normative discrepancies may be linked to the fact that teachers are expected to fulfill activities that are relatively opposed to one another. This type of role conflict has been examined in both the United States and the United Kingdom, and Grace provides a fair overview of the challenges involved (1972). Role conflicts of this fourth type have also been linked to strain. Teachers may be stressed as a result of their overworked lives, insufficient pay or bad physical conditions at school, ethnic conflict in the community, or physical violence in the school or classroom. Given the economic stagnation in many nations since the early 1970s, these latter issues appear to have worsened for teachers, and studies of role conflict have decreased in quantity as a result. Nonetheless, role conflicts continue to be a source of stress for teachers, and studies have shown that such conflicts are a key predictor of bad morale in the workplace. Role conflict is described in two ways by Rosa (1971). (1) holding two or more statuses at the same time, each having competing standards, such as familial (father) and occupational (employee) statuses. In this role conflict, the same person assumes multiple roles, either concurrently or sequentially: (2) a status's internal struggle. A status holder may discover that different people want him to fulfill his function in different ways; for example, addressing kids' needs may conflict with the expectations of parents or school authorities.

Significance of the Study:-

The current research primarily falls under the umbrella of sociology in general, women's studies in particular, and sociology of education in particular. It has become a difficult burden for women teachers in particular to cope with shifting societal demands in light of their multifaceted positions. Role conflict can also be explained as a result of physical and mental issues that cause tension, stress, and dissatisfaction. Because of the numerous societal demands, this occurs among female teachers. Working women's challenges are exacerbated by the fact that they must work in an environment that is vastly different from their own.

Furthermore, teachers face significant difficulties in performing their roles effectively in every area of life due to remote work locations and poor incomes. As a result of these issues, it is difficult to fulfill one's function efficiently in any field of life. As a result, the purpose of this study is to investigate the nature and extent of conflicting situations that have arisen as a result of working women teachers' changing roles in their families and at work, as well as the relationship between some variables such as the type of situation at school, marital status, and teaching experience in the field of education.

The study is useful for policymakers and planners, as well as feminists and educators. It is hoped that this study will spark more research in this area and that the findings will lead to better administration of the primary school system, allowing women to contribute effectively to national development. Teacher education programs will equip young female teachers to deal with these tasks in a way that reduces the stress that comes with them.

Scope of the Study:-

The current research focuses on the existing role conflict among teachers in primary schools. Primary school teachers, like other working women, suffer role conflict while doing their duties. The issue of women's employment is inextricably tied to their role in the family and the disproportionately high amount of household duty that they bear, which acts as a barrier to admittance into the teaching profession. Teachers are faced with a new set of challenges as they acclimate to their new jobs and the rigors of teaching. Working women's dual responsibilities come into conflict for a variety of reasons, resulting in role conflict. As a result, she develops a stress factor, and she frequently suffers from a guilty conscience, finding herself split between her home, school, and society. This, in turn, causes a slew of issues. The current research focuses on a thorough examination of numerous facets of conflict and challenges that arise from dual role performance.

Objectives Of The Study:-

The current research was created with the following objectives are-

1. To study the socio-economic profile of the female teacher in primary school.
2. To examine the effect of role conflict on female teacher's job performance.

Review Of The Selected Literature:-

In their study of the impact of sociodemographic variables on patient satisfaction, **Macquarie (1972)** predicted how teachers would react in various psychological situations such as role conflict. Role conflict and conflicts between teachers' needs and role expectations linked to socially dominant role behaviors were shown to be widespread in the study's findings. When predictions

of warmth and directiveness of anticipated behavior were made for specific teachers, the results of these conflicts for "self-oriented" and "other-oriented" teachers were supported.

As assessed by the headmasters, **Varma (1975)** identified role conflict scenarios. He also looked into the expectations of teachers, students, parents, and administrators from the headmaster, as well as the anxiety that the headmasters felt when they were put in role-conflict situations. There were other attempts to investigate the association between role conflict and the headmaster's personality attributes, as well as the relationship between role conflict and institutional issues. The study's findings imply that role conflict is positively associated with worry, which is strongest in scenarios involving material purchases. The frequency of congruence and incongruence between perceived role conflict and observed incompatibility in anticipation was shown to vary by situation. When headmasters were divided into two groups based on whether they worked in a boys' or girls' school, a substantial difference in role conflict was detected. When there was a lot of role conflict, the headmasters looked for compromise rather than complete conformance or avoidance. **Brenda Freeman and M. Kenneth Coll(1997)**, documented school counselor role conflict in their study which looked at elementary school counselors' self-perceptions of role conflict versus middle and secondary school counselors. The Role Questionnaire and demographic questions were included in the study survey. The findings confirmed the hypothesis that elementary school counselors feel greater role conflict than middle and high school counselors because they have more duties and functions and are in less secure positions.

Felora and Edward (1977) attempted to investigate the relationship between role conflict and ambiguity and employment participation, job happiness, job threat and anxiety, and inclination to leave. All of the connections between role conflict, role ambiguity, and the four job participation variables were significant and in the expected direction. The size and complexity of the principal's organization, as well as the principal's gender, did not affect the degree of role conflict and role ambiguity they faced. **Brown and Lamar (1978)** investigated the possible role conflict experienced by black administrators in predominantly white institutions, identifying evidence of black administrators' actual decision-making power and authority within the administrative role, and investigating those special circumstances and unique services that black administrators provide that are related to black student needs, finding black administrators had total administrative authority in their sp Administrators who were black were not expected to be considered experts on black issues. Using Robert Kahn's model of role conflict, **Porter**

and Hyden (1978) compared the perceived role conflict experienced by women secondary public school principals to the perceived role conflict experienced by men secondary public school principals. The study's findings focused on the role conflict experienced by male principals in public secondary schools vs the role conflict experienced by women principals in public secondary schools. There were variations in age, experience, marital status, and educational background, with female principals being older, less experienced, single, and having a greater level of educational training than male principals. In his study, **Mary Ann (1979)** looked at how tenure, role conflict, and role conflict resolution affected job orientation and burnout. In the projections, the frequency of role conflict was found to be a significant variable. Work orientation and tenure, role conflict, and burnout, on the other hand, did not appear to have any meaningful correlations.

Adual Kader Parambut, (2000) investigated the stress and professional efficiency of Kerala's primary school principals. The research was started to obtain a doctoral degree in education. Heads of Primary Schools, according to Parambut, experience a lot of stress while trying to meet their professional commitments. Vincent De Paul and **Karpage Kumaravel (2003)** did a study on elementary school teachers titled "Teacher Effectiveness: An Empirical Study of Elementary School Teachers, Experiments in Education," in which they discovered that certain elementary school teachers lack professional dedication. **Bhogle (1971)** attempted to quantify role conflict in teachers and to establish a link between role conflict and some personal qualities of teachers and administrators. The survey included thirty headmasters and 320 teachers from 30 schools in Hyderabad and Secunderabad. They represented a variety of schools, including government, private, aided, and boys and girls schools. According to the study's findings, headmasters with greater credentials are in a role conflict. Headmasters who earn more money have less role conflict. Role conflict is more common among experienced teachers. In research on 'Job Satisfaction among School Teachers,' **Lavingia (1974)** discovered that primary school teachers were happier than secondary school teachers, unmarried teachers were happier than married teachers, and women teachers were happier than male teachers.

Robert T. Keller (1975) attempted to investigate the relationship between role conflict, ambiguity, and job satisfaction. The study's sample consisted of 80 teachers. The study discovered that role conflict was associated with lower levels of satisfaction and advancement opportunities, as well as a negative link with role conflict. The intrinsic factor of job satisfaction was adversely correlated

with role ambiguity. **"Grosser (1984)** looked at the factors that contribute to women's role conflict. Other attempts were made to overcome the discrepancies in opinions toward women's roles held by diverse role models significant to others, based on role conflict theory and supporting studies. Role conflict was also investigated about several demographic characteristics. A snowball sampling design was used to distribute a questionnaire with mostly fixed replies. 286 women responded to the survey. The findings revealed that role conflict did exist, but that previous contributory factors have changed or no longer apply to the current group; no changes in role conflict were discovered due to differences in job organization. Role conflict had no correlations with marital status, income level, race/ethnicity, age, or occupational position. 2" In the study 'Effect of characteristics such as sex and marital status on the level of job-satisfaction among primary school teachers,' **Dixit (1985)** found that He discovered that female teachers are happier than male teachers and that marital status has no bearing on teacher work satisfaction.

June Irene (1985) investigated the 'effect of selected variables on role conflict as perceived by teacher/coaches in small higher education institutions.' Role Conflict was thought to be a mechanism for explaining conflictual human behavior in social organizations. There were three types of role conflicts considered:

1. Inter-sender role conflict occurs when two or more members of the role set have opposing expectations for a particular individual.
2. Intra-sender role conflict occurs when one member of the role set has opposing expectations for a certain person.
3. Personal role conflict occurs when members of a role set's expectations clash with an individual's needs, values, and capabilities (Katz and Kahn, 1966). The participants were 935 randomly selected teachers/coaches who worked at small colleges and universities in the fall of 1984. None of the variables studied had a significant impact on the individuals' intra-sender role conflict scores. However, in both inter-sender and personal role conflict, the desired role made a considerable difference. According to the findings, individuals who choose the single role of coaching have considerably more inter-sender and person role conflict than those who favor the dual role of teaching and coaching. 3"

Srivastava Shobha (1986) investigated the association between elementary school teachers' job happiness and professional honesty. The study discovered that young teachers had much higher job satisfaction than older teachers. Teachers with high academic accomplishment were more satisfied with

their jobs than those with low academic achievement.

Need of the Study:-

Due to the inappropriate delivery of traditional healthcare services, particularly in public hospitals, patients and their families regularly express unhappiness with the care they receive in hospitals. Furthermore, maintaining or fostering a relationship with patients is not a long-term behavioural aim in public hospitals. Determining how hospital healthcare services affect patient satisfaction and behavioural intention is the goal of the current study. The conduct of nurses and doctors is essential to providing patients with high-quality medical care. By highlighting healthcare service inadequacies and the intents of nurses and doctors toward their patients, the study's findings can help organizations improve their public image and hospital healthcare services.

A conference will be scheduled to prepare the data with more authority after conducting this research. Because they will receive medical care that enhances their health, patients will gain from this study. "The outcomes of a consumer evaluation process in which he compares his beliefs with the help he has received." The patient is satisfied if the perceived performance fulfils their service expectations, as determined by comparing their expectations to the actual performance.

Methods:-

Sampling and Data Analysis: Sampling is one of the most important steps in any research work. The sample represents the accurate characteristic that is

being examined of the population of the study area. The researcher has found several categories of primary schools; those are Rural, Urban Primary Schools, Government, Aided, and Unaided Schools. Hence stratified random sampling method was considered the best option for the present study. The sample size is 300. For the data collection, the researcher took permission from the administrators of the schools, the researcher went to selected schools in Meerut District. The objectives of the research were explained to the teacher and they were taken into confidence that their answers not affect their work and life, and the answers given by them would be kept confidential. After that questionnaire with scales was distributed to primary school female teachers and it was filled by teachers in the presence and absence of the researcher. The researcher also clarified the doubts raised by the respondent.

Area of the Study: Teachers who are teaching at primary schools in Meerut District constitute the universe of the present study. (The population of the present study included all those female teachers who are teaching at the primary school in Meerut District).

Result and Discussion:-

The analysis and interpretation of the research data are presented in this section. One of the most important steps in the research process is data analysis and interpretation. Using proper statistical tools and techniques, the researcher analyzes the data based on the research objectives.

Table-1
Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Variables	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Age		
21-25 yrs	50	16.67%
26-30 yrs	35	11.67%
31-35 yrs	40	13.33%
36-40 yrs	60	20%
41-45 yrs	70	23.33%
46-50 yrs	20	6.67%
51-55 yrs	15	5%
56 and above	10	3.33%
Religion		
Hindu	150	50%
Muslim	85	28.33%
Christian	65	21.67%
Category		
SC	65	21.67%
ST	40	13.33%
OBC	100	33.33%
GEN	95	31.67%
Marital Status		
Unmarried	125	41.67%
Married	75	25%
Widow	100	33.33%
Types of Family		

Joint	175	58.33%
Nuclear	125	41.67%
Number of Children		
Nil	105	35%
One	40	13.33%
Two	130	43.33%
Three and Above	25	8.33%
Annual Income		
Below 100000	70	23.33%
100000-200000	145	48.33%
Above 200000	85	28.33%

Source: Data collected by the researcher himself during Jan.-Apr. 2022.

The majority of the people who answered the survey, 58.33%, were in the middle age group of 36 and above; half of the respondents are Hindu; approximately 2/3rd (68.33%) belong to the OBC SC ST category, which shows the lower status in

society; a large number (41.67%) are unmarried; and the majority (58.33%) of the respondents are unmarried, in which those who are married have two or more children within the 1 lakh to 2 lakh annual income group.

Table-2: Different Levels of Role Conflict Dimensions among the Respondents

Sl. No.	Dimensions of Role Conflict	Level	Frequency	Percentage(%)
1	Individual versus Family	Low	135	45
		Moderate	40	13.33
		High	125	41.67
Total			300	100

According to the data in Table 2, Serial number 1, 45 percent of female teachers have a low degree of individual vs family role conflict, 13.33 percent have a moderate level of role conflict, and

the remaining 41.66 percent have a high level of individual versus family role conflict. Individual versus family role conflict is moderate for the majority of female teachers.

Sl. No.	Dimensions of Role Conflict	Level	Frequency	Percentage(%)
2	Family versus Individual	Low	145	48.34
		Moderate	100	33.33
		High	55	18.33
Total			300	100

According to the data in Table 2, Serial number 2, 48.33 percent of female teachers have a low degree of family vs individual role conflict, 33.33 percent have a moderate level of role conflict,

and the remaining 18.33 percent have a high level of family versus individual role conflict. The majority of female teachers had moderate family versus individual role conflict.

Sl. No.	Dimensions of Role Conflict	Level	Frequency	Percentage(%)
3	Individual versus School	Low	120	40
		Moderate	150	50
		High	30	10
Total			300	100

According to the data shown in Table 2, Serial number 3, 40 percent of female teachers have low individual against-school-role conflict, 50 percent have moderate individual versus school-role

conflict, and the remaining 10% have significant individual versus school-role conflict. Individual versus School Role Conflict is moderate for the majority of female teachers.

Sl. No.	Dimensions of Role Conflict	Level	Frequency	Percentage(%)
4	School versus Individual	Low	100	33.33
		Moderate	105	35
		High	95	31.67
Total			300	100

According to the data in Table 2, Serial number 4, 33.33 percent of female teachers have a

low degree of school vs individual role conflict, 35 percent have a moderate level of role conflict, and

the remaining 31.66 percent have a high level of school versus individual role conflict. The majority

of female teachers had a moderate level of school versus individual role conflict.

Sl. No.	Dimensions of Role Conflict	Level	Frequency	Percentage(%)
5	Individual versus Society	Low	110	36.67
		Moderate	150	50
		High	40	13.33
Total			300	100

According to the data in Table 2, Serial number 5, 36.66 percent of female teachers have a low degree of individual vs society role conflict, 50 percent have a moderate level of role conflict, and

the remaining 13.33 percent have a high level of individual versus society role conflict. Individual versus societal role conflict is moderate for the majority of female teachers.

Sl. No.	Dimensions of Role Conflict	Level	Frequency	Percentage(%)
6	Society versus Individual	Low	122	40.66
		Moderate	85	28.33
		High	93	31
Total			300	100

According to the statistics in Table 2, Serial number 6, 40.66 percent of female teachers have low individual vs society role conflict, while 28.33 percent of female teachers have high individual versus society role conflict. The level of role

conflict is moderate, and the remaining 31% of female teachers have a high level of society vs individual role conflict. The majority of female teachers have a moderate society versus individual role conflict.

Sl. No.	Dimensions of Role Conflict	Level	Frequency	Percentage(%)
7	Family versus School	Low	115	38.33
		Moderate	55	18.33
		High	130	43.33
Total			300	100

According to the data in Table 2, Serial number 7, 38.33 percent of female teachers have a low degree of family against school role conflict, 18.33 percent have a moderate level of role conflict,

and the rest 43.33 percent have a high level of family versus school role conflict. The majority of female teachers have a moderate family versus school duty conflict.

Sl. No.	Dimensions of Role Conflict	Level	Frequency	Percentage(%)
8	School versus Family	Low	105	35
		Moderate	125	41.67
		High	70	23.33
Total			300	100

According to the data in Table 2, Serial number 8, 35 percent of female teachers have a low degree of school against family role conflict, 41.66 percent have a moderate level of role conflict, and

the remaining 23.33 percent have a high level of school versus family role conflict. School versus family role conflict is moderate for the majority of female teachers.

Sl. No.	Dimensions of Role Conflict	Level	Frequency	Percentage(%)
9	Family versus Society	Low	15	8.33
		Moderate	115	38.33
		High	160	53.33
Total			300	100

According to the data in Table 2, Serial number 9, 8.33 percent of female teachers have a low degree of family vs school role conflict, 38.33 percent have a moderate level of role conflict, and

the rest 53.33 percent have a high level of family versus society role conflict. The majority of female teachers' role conflict between family and society is moderate.

Sl. No.	Dimensions of Role Conflict	Level	Frequency	Percentage(%)
10	Society versus Family	Low	50	16.66
		Moderate	175	56.66
		High	80	26.66
Total			300	100

According to the data in Table 2, Serial

number 10, 16.66 percent of female teachers have a

low level of society versus family role conflict, 56.66 percent have a moderate level of society versus family role conflict, and the remaining 26.66

percent have a high level of society versus family role conflict. The majority of female teachers have a moderate society versus family role conflict.

Sl. No.	Dimensions of Role Conflict	Level	Frequency	Percentage(%)
11	School versus Society	Low	145	48.33
		Moderate	70	23.33
		High	85	28.33
Total			300	100

According to the data in Table 2, Serial number 11, 48.33 percent of female teachers have a low level of school-versus-society role conflict, 23.33 percent have a moderate level of school-

versus-society role conflict, and the remaining 28.33 percent have a high level of school versus society role conflict. The majority of female teachers' role conflict between school and society is moderate.

Sl. No.	Dimensions of Role Conflict	Level	Frequency	Percentage(%)
12	Society versus School	Low	115	38.33
		Moderate	65	21.66
		High	120	40
Total			300	100

According to the data in Table 2, Serial number 12, 38.33 percent of female teachers have a low level of society vs school role conflict, 21.66 percent have a moderate level of society versus school role conflict, and the remaining 40% have a high level of society versus school role conflict. The majority of female teachers have a moderate society versus school role conflict.

Conclusion:-

The current study demonstrates the variables that influenced the role conflict among female primary school teachers. Role conflict and socioeconomic position do not significantly correlate. Conflict tendencies are more psychological and attitudinal, therefore one's natural ability to be accommodating and how they view the circumstance have a big impact. According to the study, primary school female permanent teachers experience more role conflict than temporary female primary school teachers. Permanent teachers must perform many tasks because they are required to do so by state government laws, particularly in government-aided schools where there is a shortage of administrative staff. According to the findings, there is no discernible difference between female primary school teachers' religious affiliation and the mean score of role conflict. Even though it is a societal fact, religion has little impact on teachers' day-to-day lives in formal educational institutions.

The institution of marriage is significant in society. It not only causes a shift in status but also assumes varied duties and responsibilities for every spare member of the family. Because married female teachers have more obligations than single counterparts, marital status may affect role conflict. According to the current study, married female teachers in primary schools experience more role conflict than their single counterparts. The research of Latha Kumari (1991), who looked at the role conflict among female secondary school teachers,

supports this conclusion. Married teachers have considerably more role conflict than single teachers, according to the study's findings. Due to their multiple responsibilities for work and family, married working women were shown to be at higher risk than men (1987). The role conflict could be impacted by the female teachers' caste. Female teachers from upper castes may encounter less role conflict because their families are generally in better shape than those from lower castes. Female primary school teachers in the SC category experience more role conflict than their counterparts in the ST, OBC, and GM categories.

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Female teachers in private schools experience more role conflict than their counterparts in aided and government schools. As a result, the workload for female teachers can be lighter.
2. To ensure a positive working environment for female teachers, role conflicts have a substantial impact on job satisfaction.
3. To lessen role conflict, set up counseling services for female teachers.
4. Role conflicts are a problem for many female teachers. Set up a yoga class and free time for them to minimize their role conflict and mental tension.
5. Female teachers' families and college professors should make the appropriate adjustments.
6. Female teachers may benefit from the implementation of more lenient transfer criteria.
7. To assist female primary school teachers in methodically doing their duties, special training programs should be set up.
8. Private school teachers should get salaries comparable to those of public school teachers.
9. Teachers should have regular orientation sessions on effective communication, academic planning, and time management.

Suggestions For Future Research:-

1. Comparable studies can be carried out in other states and districts.
2. Role conflict-related factors like role strain, role stress, and work commitment are also amenable to co-relational analysis.
3. Comparative research can be done between primary school teachers and high school teachers, as well as on secondary school and college professors.
4. It is possible to research the impact of role conflict at home and school.
5. It is possible to compare teachers who are male and female.
6. Research can be conducted to understand the issues facing female teachers and the impact of role conflict.

Research can be done to determine why socioeconomic status and role conflict do not significantly relate to one another.

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